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IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY FOR ASSESSING QUALITY AND EFFICIENCY IN THE SERVICE SECTOR

Usmanova Nasiba Akbarjonovna - Independent Researcher at the Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service. Uzbekistan

Abstract: The service sector in the world economy has a sustainable development trend, and special attention is paid to research in this area. In this regard, scientific areas such as improving the quality and efficiency of services, researching modern models of quality management, assessment of seasonality in the activities of hotels, improving innovative methods of improving quality in the industry, increasing the competitiveness of service enterprises are important. In the context of innovative development of the economy, the introduction of modern methods of improving the quality of services is an important means of achieving economic efficiency. Accordingly, the study of modern approaches to improving the quality and efficiency of services, the introduction of methods to improve the quality of services, improving the efficiency of service enterprises, improving the service delivery process, developing service quality indicators, improving innovative methods of improving quality and competitiveness.

Keywords: quality, efficiency, service, quality of service, indicators of quality, methods of evaluation, efficiency of innovation, profitability of innovative activity.

Introduction. The development of the service sector in the world as a global trend is an important factor in the growth of GDP and the main mechanism of employment. In most countries, there is a tendency to increase the volume of services, increase revenues from services, increase competition in this area, increase exports and imports of services.

As a leading sector of the economy, the volume of trade in services in the world has increased fivefold over the past two decades. In developed countries, the share of services in GDP is 3/4, 75.0% of employment and 2/3 of capital investments and investments in fixed assets account for services.

The service sector in the world economy has a sustainable development trend, and special attention is paid to research in this area. In this regard, scientific areas such as improving the quality and efficiency of services, researching modern models of quality management, assessment of seasonality in the activities of hotels, improving innovative methods of improving quality in the industry, increasing the competitiveness of service enterprises are important.

In the context of innovative development of the economy, the introduction of modern methods of improving the quality of services is an important means of achieving economic efficiency. Accordingly, the study of modern approaches to improving the quality and efficiency of services, the introduction of methods to improve the quality of services, improving the efficiency of service enterprises, improving the service delivery process, developing service quality indicators, improving innovative methods of improving quality and competitiveness. Special attention is paid to such issues as.

In the Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Oliy Majlis, "Privileges in the field of tourism, transport and catering will be extended until the end of next year. I also propose to extend the deadline for the payment of land and property taxes by 20 entrepreneurs for another 400 billion soums for another year. In solving these tasks, it is important to study modern models of quality management in the service sector, to analyze the indicators of quality and efficiency in the hotel industry, to deepen research in areas such as increasing the competitiveness of enterprises.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan August 13, 2019 PF-5781 "On measures to further develop the tourism sector in the Republic of Uzbekistan" and PF-5813 dated September 6, 2019 "On the introduction of modern information technology in the system of settlements in trade and services and strengthening public control in this area." This dissertation research will serve to a certain extent in the implementation of the tasks set out in the decrees of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Concept of Tourism Development in 2019-2025" and other relevant regulations in this area.

Theoretical foundations and practical issues of the development of the service sector were studied by foreign scientists, including: K.H. Haksever, B.R. Render, RS Russell, R.G. Merdik, J.A. Romanov, O.P. Efimova, Researched by G.A. Avanesova et al. M.E. Pulatov, D.R. Zaynalov, K.J. Mirzaev, B.Sh. Safarov, B.A. Adukarimov, D. Aslanova, and others.

However, in the research work of these economists, the service sector, methods of assessing quality and efficiency in hotels, modern models of quality management in the service sector, as well as innovative methods of improving the quality of services and competitiveness factors are not sufficiently studied. Currently, the importance and insufficient study of research related to improving the quality and efficiency in the field of services allows to determine the relevance of the dissertation topic, its purpose and main objectives.

The purpose of the study is to develop scientifically based proposals and recommendations to improve the competitiveness of enterprises in the industry based on the improvement of the system of quality and efficiency assessment in the service sector.

Research objectives is formation of the author's approach on the basis of scientific and theoretical research of the essence of the categories "service", "quality of services" and "efficiency"; identification of methods for assessing quality and efficiency in the field of services; research of modern models of quality management in the field of services; analysis of development trends and factors in the service sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan; analysis and assessment of factors affecting seasonality in the activities of hotel farms; analysis of indicators of quality and efficiency in the hotel industry; improvement of innovative ways to improve the quality of services; identification of ways to improve the quality management system of hotel services; Development of scientifically based conclusions and recommendations on the main directions of improving the competitiveness of service enterprises. The scientific novelty of the research is: the system of indicators representing the composition of the characteristics of the quality of services in service enterprises is classified on the basis of the formation of a group of functional indicators, safety indicators, performance indicators and professional level indicators of employees; the method of evaluating the effectiveness of innovations based on the comparison of results with costs in the service sector has been improved on the basis of indicators that reflect the integrated economic efficiency, profitability of innovative activities, cost-effectiveness of innovations; developed a block diagram model of achieving economic efficiency in the service quality management system based on ensuring the safety and timeliness of services, timely provision of services, risk reduction for society and the individual, and the introduction of innovations; the methodology for assessing the quality and competitiveness of hotel services has been improved on the basis of adaptation to changes in the competitive environment in the services market, the formation of a classification of competitiveness and quality indicators that take into account aspects related to customer satisfaction.

The practical results of the study are as follows: developed an author's definition of the categories "service", "quality of services" and "efficiency", which are important criteria for the development of the service sector; developed a model of quality management system based on a process approach to increasing the responsibility of management, resource management, periodic analysis of the quality management system and decision-making on its development; the model of audit of

service quality is proposed on the basis of definition of the list of services and quality indicators, collection of information on quality of services, formation of its database and improvement of system of management of innovations on quality of services in the enterprise.

Reliability of research results. The reliability of the survey results is determined by the appropriateness of the approaches and methods used, the data obtained from official sources, including statistics from the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, hotel reports and the implementation of relevant conclusions and recommendations by the authorities.

Scientific and practical significance of research results. The scientific significance of the research results is explained by the proposals and recommendations developed in the dissertation to improve the methodology for assessing the quality and efficiency of service enterprises, seasonality in hotel operations, improving the quality of services, enriching the scientific apparatus.

The practical significance of the results is explained by the fact that they can be used to assess quality and efficiency in the service sector, improve innovative methods of quality improvement, prepare regulatory documents in the field, as well as develop a set of measures for the development of service enterprises and hotels. The results of the research can be used in the teaching of science programs and subjects such as "Enterprise Management", "Quality Management", "Organization of Quality Management", "Tourism and Hotel Management", "Quality Management in Hotel Management", "Hotel Marketing".

Implementation of research results. Based on the scientific results obtained to improve the quality and efficiency of service enterprises:

The classification of the system of indicators reflecting the composition of service quality characteristics in service enterprises based on the formation of a group of functional indicators, safety indicators, performance indicators and professional indicators of employees was adopted for use in the ministry. The use of this proposal allowed to increase the scope of assessment of the quality of services in service enterprises by the composition and structure of the described features by 1.5 times;

The proposal to improve the method of evaluating the effectiveness of innovations based on the comparison of costs and results in the service sector on the basis of indicators of integrated economic efficiency, profitability of innovative activities, cost-effectiveness of innovations was adopted for use in the practice of the reference of the Ministry of Sports. The use of this proposal allowed to increase the economic efficiency of the introduction of innovations based on the systematization of indicators used in the service sector by 125.0%;

Block diagram model of economic efficiency in the service quality management system based on ensuring the safety and timeliness of services, timely provision of services, risk reduction for society and the individual, and the introduction of innovations Department of the Ministry. This model allowed to analyze and monitor the impact of each formalized process on the specific indicators of the efficiency of the service enterprise, to calculate the economic efficiency from the introduction into the quality management system;

The proposal to improve the methodology for assessing the quality and competitiveness of hotel services on the basis of adaptation to changes in the competitive environment in the services market, the formation of a classification of competitiveness and quality indicators that take into account aspects of customer satisfaction was accepted for use in practice. The use of this proposal allowed to determine the relationship between the quality of hotel services and their competitiveness in the services market.

Based on the specific characteristics of enterprises operating in all sectors and industries of the economy, service enterprises also have their own characteristics and features. Accordingly, it is expedient to show the peculiarities of the development of this field, which represent the choice of certain factors.

The concept of quality applies to both goods and services and the process of production of goods and services. Any product or service must meet the specific requirements of consumers.

Quality of services is a general description of services that determines the satisfaction of the identified or intended needs of the consumer. The quality of services often depends on the quality of services provided to consumers.

The quality of services is an important indicator of the company's performance, and its improvement is an indicator of intensive development, which is determined by the survival of the company in the market, the pace of scientific and technological progress, increased production efficiency, saving all kinds of resources.

Efficiency is a complex socio-economic category, which represents the achievement of a certain efficiency of the production (service) process in order to achieve high results in one or another area of economic activity and reduce costs per unit of this result.

In the context of economic transformation, the sustainable development of the service sector is directly related to the improvement of traditional services and the diversification of new types of services based on modern and digital technologies. This is because the quality and efficiency of services will increase only if the

development of this industry is optimal under the influence of innovative factors and flexible in terms of market services.

The development of the digital economy is also having an impact on the service sector. The total volume of services in Samarkand region in 2020 will reach 1318.7 billion soums. This figure increased by 82.3% compared to 2016. The highest growth rates by type of services were in the field of architecture, engineering research, technical testing and analysis - 5.9 times, in financial services - 4.0 times, in educational services - 2.5 times, in accommodation and catering services - 2.4. times, in health services - 2.1 times.

In our country, as in all types of economic activity, structural changes are taking place in the service sector. In particular, in January-December 2020, 14 trillion soums will be spent in the region. 318.7 billion UZS, the growth rate compared to the same period last year was 102.6%.

Research shows that in the study of demand for services in Samarkand region and the provision of quality services, it is important to work in the following areas: development of scientific and practical manuals and guidelines for studying the process of supply and demand for new types of services; to have the necessary information for the analysis of the conjuncture of services at the regional level and to prepare relevant reports, booklets and reports to increase the demand for services, in particular tourist services; conducting questionnaires and sociological surveys to assess the quality of services provided; organization of various social events and participation in fairs, exhibitions in order to solve existing problems in the field of services.

Continuous improvement of quality – is a promising investment, ensuring the formation of a constant flow of customers. This was confirmed in the research work, where the cost of attracting a new customer is 10 times higher than the cost of re-attracting a regular customer. Therefore, it is an important task to retain regular customers through quality service.

The modern model of quality management of hotel services in Uzbekistan is implemented within a separate enterprise without external influences. Also, the quality management of the resources entering the system is practically non-existent, and the quality control at the exit of the system is carried out with delays on the basis of feedback. Of the quality management functions, only control is exercised and emphasis is placed on whether the main placement tools belong to a particular category.

The methodology for assessing the quality and competitiveness of hotel services has been improved on the basis of adaptation to changes in the competitive

environment in the services market, the formation of a classification of competitiveness and quality indicators that take into account aspects related to customer satisfaction.

This methodology is also designed to assess the competitiveness of services related to the quality of services, and shows the existing relationship between service quality indicators and their competitiveness in the services market includes the following steps: Phase 1. Assess the competitiveness of the hotel business and its competitors and identify strategic factors; Phase 2. Identify the main competitors of the hotel business on the basis of creating a strategic group of competitors and a competitive map; Step 3. Identification of competing services and based on them a map of the strategic group of services will be created; Step 4. The competitiveness of hotel organizations is based on the position of the organizations on the basis of the competitive map of the market; Step 5. Determining the level of service quality on the scale of customer satisfaction and admiration for hotel services; Step 6. Segmentation of the hotel business market by the needs and capabilities of consumers of hotel services; Step 7. Assessment of the financial performance of the hotel business; Step 8. Determining the relationship between competitiveness indicators and quality indicators; Step 9. Comparison of the quality of services of the hotel enterprise on limited indicators; Step 10. Determining a comprehensive indicator of the quality of hotel services; Step 11. Based on the importance and value of quality indicators, it is possible to determine a complex indicator of the quality of services; Step 12. Assessing the competitiveness of a hotel based on the criteria of the classification system of hotels and other accommodation facilities. Practical recommendations have been developed for the development of consumer-oriented marketing concepts of service enterprises, analysis and evaluation of enterprise competitiveness, acceleration of innovation processes in the industry, classification of types of competitive strategies and implementation of comprehensive measures to form strategic competitiveness.

As a result of research conducted in the dissertation, the following conclusions, recommendations and practical recommendations were developed:

1. The research developed an author's definition of the categories "service", "quality of services" and "efficiency", which are important criteria for the development of the service sector. Services are a form of economic activity that does not have a material description, cannot be maintained, and as a result of actions that take place simultaneously in the process of production and consumption, meet the needs of consumers in a specific place and time and create value. Quality of services is a general description of services that determines the satisfaction of the identified

or intended needs of the consumer. Efficiency is a complex socio-economic category, which represents the achievement of a certain efficiency of the production (service) process in order to achieve high results in one or another area of economic activity and reduce costs per unit of this result.

2. The system of indicators representing the composition of service quality characteristics in service enterprises is classified on the basis of the formation of a group of functional indicators, safety indicators, performance indicators and professional level indicators of employees.

3. The method of evaluating the effectiveness of innovations based on the comparison of results with costs in the service sector has been improved on the basis of indicators that reflect the integrated economic efficiency, profitability of innovative activities, cost-effectiveness of innovations.

4. A systematic approach to quality management requires firms to analyze consumer demand, identify the processes by which products, works and services are created, as well as bring them to a level where they can manage these processes. Accordingly, a model of quality management system based on a process approach to increasing the responsibility of enterprise management, resource management, periodic analysis of the quality management system and decision-making on development has been developed.

5. The process of quality assessment in hotel facilities has been improved on the basis of assessing the adequacy of accommodation facilities and hotel rooms by category, the effectiveness of services provided by accommodation facilities and the classification of rooms by additional requirements.

6. Reducing seasonality in tourism is an important issue. Therefore, it is necessary to increase the tourism potential of the regions, to ensure the attractiveness of tourists, to hold conferences and fairs in the winter, and thus to develop an action plan to reduce the seasonality factor.

7. Conclusions on the correlation analysis of the competitiveness of hotel services on the basis of mathematical and statistical methods of analysis and evaluation of their competitiveness show that the competitiveness of hotel enterprises and the reliability of service quality have a significant impact on increasing market share.

8. The efficiency of service enterprises is directly related to the scientific organization of their organizational, managerial and economic processes, which include: planning the activities of the enterprise, developing a development strategy appropriate to changes in supply and demand in the services market or the range of services; assessment of production and non-production costs of services at the

enterprise; modernization of the structure of technological processes and technical means, taking into account the range and quality of services; selection and involvement of specialists with socio-psychological abilities to determine the opinion of consumers; improving the professional skills and qualifications of service personnel; evaluation of service cost efficiency; increase service results.

9. A model of service quality audit based on the definition of the list and quality indicators of services, the collection of information on the quality of services, the formation of its database and the improvement of the management system of innovation in the quality of services in the enterprise.

10. A block diagram model of economic efficiency in the service quality management system has been developed on the basis of ensuring the safety and timeliness of services, timely provision of services, risk reduction for society and each individual, and the introduction of innovations.

11. The methodology for assessing the quality and competitiveness of hotel services has been improved on the basis of adaptation to changes in the competitive environment in the services market, the formation of a classification of competitiveness and quality indicators that take into account aspects related to customer satisfaction.

12. Developed practical recommendations for the development of consumer-oriented marketing concepts of service enterprises, analysis and evaluation of enterprise competitiveness, acceleration of innovation processes in the field, classification of types of competitive strategies and implementation of comprehensive measures to form strategic competitiveness.

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